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ME- 366

(ELECTRO-MECHANICAL SYSTEM DESIGN SESSIONAL)

PROJECT TITLE

**GPS BASED SPEED REGULATION SYSTEM FOR VEHICLE IN
RESTRICTED AREA.**

SUBMITTED BY

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Abstract:

In our project, we developed a device that can track a vehicle's location and speed. If speed is beyond a certain limit in a restricted zone, a monetary penalty will be sent via SMS. The purpose of this device is to increase the alertness of the driver and reduce the number of accidents on roads of our country. We measured speed and location utilizing a GPS module and display speed and the distance from the nearest restricted point in an OLED screen. So, when the vehicle is near the restricted area, if speed of vehicle is beyond a certain limit, the driver will be sent an SMS to reduce speed within safe limit. If he does not obey the speed limitation, he will receive a monetary penalty.

1 Introduction

Road accident is a common incident in Bangladesh nowadays. The reasons for these accidents, on the driver sight, are:

- Reckless Driving
- Sleeping during driving
- Lack of alertness during driving etc.

Due to these reasons, many lives are being lost every day on the road, just in a blink of an eye. Traffic rules are not strict in our country. Moreover, there is nobody to look over the highways. The drivers never obey traffic rules and regulations on highways. Besides, there are many accidental areas such as the junction of three or four roads, in front of the school, college, market, hospital, etc., where controlling speed within a specific limit is necessary. But unfortunately, the drivers do not maintain it. As a result, news of accidents and death are being a regular occurrence in our country.

GPS (Global Positioning System) is an invaluable technology used to accurately measure the speed and location of vehicles in a multitude of applications. In the automotive industry, GPS is integrated into navigation systems and fleet management solutions to provide real-time speed and location data. So, we want to ensure more control over this sector utilizing GPS technology. Our project is to make a device that can track a vehicle's position and if the vehicle is in any accidental zone, where speed must be limited, it will alert the drivers and will measure the speed of vehicles. If speed is beyond certain safety limit, it will register a monetary penalty for that vehicle's number.

Due to fear of this penalty, the drivers will be alert all the time about the restricted area and about his vehicle's speed, reckless driving will be reduced. If we can implement this device on our highways, we hope that number of road accidents will be largely reduced.

2 Background and Literature Review

As a country of big population and weaker road transportation system, road accident is a regular phenomenon. According to a report of the Accident Research Institute of BUET, about 56987 people were being killed by 58280 road accidents across our country in the last two decades.

Intelligent Speed Adaptation (ISA) is being tested in many countries for a long time. Many systems have been developed for auditory and visual warning or a counterforce by the accelerator pedal or prevention of speeding by regulation of the fuel braking system.

Lahrmann et al. [1] presented a research project at Aalborg University in Denmark. The research project has developed an ISA-system (hardware and software). The system has been tested by 24 test drivers. The purpose of the test is to collect users' reactions to the system. The project has also investigated how the user's speed changes when an ISA system is installed in their cars. The ISA system establishes the position of the car, and the position is compared with a digital roadmap that contains the local speed limits. If the local speed limit is exceeded the system responds through a LED flash. The UK External Vehicle Speed Control (EVSC) project has predicted the accident savings with intelligent speed adaptation (ISA) and estimated the costs and benefits of national implementation studied by Carlsen and Tate [2]. The best prediction of accident reduction was that the fitting on all vehicles of a simple mandatory system, with which it would be impossible for vehicles to exceed the speed limit, would save 20% of injury accidents and 37% of fatal accidents. A more complex version of the mandatory system, including a capability to respond to current network and weather conditions, would result in a reduction of 36% in injury accidents and 59% in fatal accidents. The implementation path recommended by the project would lead to compulsory usage in 2019. The cost-benefit analysis carried out showed that the benefit-cost ratios for this implementation strategy were in a range from 7.9 to 15.4, i.e., the payback for the system could be up to 15 times the cost of implementing and running it. H. L Oei et al. [3] showed the experimental result of ISA technology. Experiments in Sweden are tested several options, from warning the driver to a resisting force exerted by the accelerator pedal that can be countered by the driver. In the Netherlands, the system intervenes so the limit cannot be exceeded. Experiments in Sweden have recently been concluded and an evaluation is in progress. In the Netherlands, the project was concluded early 2001. The field experiments so far mainly concern the measure of acceptance of the systems by the public. Several simulation studies have also been conducted. Little is known as yet from practical research of the effects of ISA on road safety, though a large safety potential is assumed. For the Dutch situation, based on the assumption that all passenger cars are fitted with ISA and an assumed speed distribution as the result of ISA, a theoretical calculation is made of the effects of ISA on speed and safety. The result is an estimated reduction of road casualties of 25 to 30%. Further, the assumed speed distribution is validated with field measurements of the experiment in the city of Tilburg. The first field experiment with intelligent speed adaptation (ISA) in Malaysia was carried in December 2010 in the State of Penang by Ghadiri et al. [4]. Eleven private cars were instrumented with an advisory system. The study included a vocal warning message and a visual text message that is activated when the driver attempts to exceed the speed limit. When the driver decreases the speed, the warning stops; otherwise, it is continuously repeated. The test drivers drove the vehicles for three months with the installed system, and the speed was continuously logged in all vehicles. The warning was however only activated in the second month of the three months. The study aimed to evaluate the effects of an advisory ISA on driving speed, traffic safety, and drivers' attitude, behavior, and acceptance of the system. To examine these effects, both the survey and the logged speed data were analyzed and explored. The results show a significant reduction in the mean, maximum, and 85th percentile speed due to the use of the system. However, there was no long-lasting effect on the speed when the system was deactivated. In the post-trial survey, drivers declared

that the system helped them well in following the speed limits and that it assisted them in driving more comfortably. Furthermore, the warning method was more accepted compared to a supportive system, such as an active accelerator pedal (AAP). After the trial, most drivers were willing to keep an ISA system.

All these papers described the benefits of intelligent speed adaptation (ISA) technology. The main constraint of implementing this technology is on the driver side. Since the monetary penalty is an issue with our proposed idea, the transport companies may not be willing to accept this technology.

3 Theory

GPS module is the main component of our device. The GPS consists of three segments:

- The space segment: the GPS satellites
- The control system, operated by the U.S. military,
- The user segment, which includes both military and civilian users and their GPS equipment.

At least 4 signal is needed to be gathered to get an accurate position on the earth. The working/operation of the Global positioning system is based on the '**trilateration**' mathematical principle. The position is determined from the distance measurements to satellites. At present, GPS receivers are very accurate and their accuracy mainly depends on numerous variables which include the ionosphere, the available satellites, the urban environment, etc. Some factors obstruct GPS accuracy like physical obstruction (buildings, mountains, trees), atmospheric effects (solar storm, heavy storm cover, ionospheric effect) etc.

GSM is another communication technology we have used in the project. The Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) is a standard developed by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) to describe the protocols for second-generation (2G) digital cellular networks used by mobile devices such as mobile phones and tablets.

4 Tools

- Arduino Uno as Microcontrollers.
- LED and Buzzers as alert systems.
- Tinygps++ library to process NMEA format GPS data.
- Proteus simulation software to design final circuit.
- GPS & GSM modules.

5 Design and Methodology

We want to track a vehicle's location and speed (measurement issue in the project) during its ride and compare if it is in the restricted zone with risky speed or not and send penalty SMS if speed is

higher than a recommended speed. Our project is mainly electrical component-based. So, coding and circuit diagram is the main design procedure.

5.1 Circuit Design

Figure 1. Circuit Diagram

Connections of devices:

Neo 6m GPS	Arduino UNO
VCC	3.3 V
TX	Digital 4
GND	GND

OLED Module	Arduino Uno
VCC	5V
GND	GND
SDA	Analog 4
SCL	Analog 5

SIM 800L module	Arduino Uno
VCC	4.3 V (Voltage reduction from 5V through a diode)
GND	GND
RXD	Digital 2
TXD	Digital 3

Besides, there are three LEDs and a buzzer, connected to digital pins 8,9,10, and 11.

5.2 Coding Strategy

- The restricted points (latitude, longitude, recommended velocity) are predefined in the code as an array.
- If GPS data is available, we will ensure if the location is valid. In general, if it is connected to at least 4 satellites, it gives a valid location.
- It tracks the nearest location point and measures distance.
 - If the nearest distance > 500 m, the vehicle is in a safe zone. The green LED will blink.
 - If $300\text{m} < \text{nearest distance} < 500$ m, then the yellow LED will blink to alert the driver that there is a restricted point in front or back of the vehicle.
 - If nearest distance < 300 m, then red LED will blink, and if the vehicle's speed is greater than the recommended speed at this location, an SMS will be sent to the respected mobile number.

- After sending a penalty SMS to any number, the program will stop for 10 seconds to give chance to the driver to reduce the vehicle's speed.
- The distance and speed will always be shown on an OLED screen.

[N.B: All these distance criteria are just arbitrarily taken just to show a prototype]

6 Calculations

Power consumption calculation:

We have used a 9 V 450mAh battery for our project.

According to the given datasheet [5] of Neo 6m GPS- its operating current is 45 mA at an operating voltage of 2.7-3.7 voltage.

According to provided data for a 96" OLED display, the operating current is 12 mA at an operating voltage of 5V

And, SIM800L module has different consumption rates at different states-

- sleep mode < 2.0mA
- idle mode < 7.0mA
- GSM transmission (avg): 350 mA
- GSM transmission (peek): 2000mA

Since this module will be in sleep or idle mode for the maximum time, let the average current consumption rate is 10 mA

So, total power consumption rate is=(45+12+10) mA = 67 mA

So, the total lifetime of this device approximately is = $450/67 = 6.71$ hours.

Distance Calculation:

Distance between two geographical points is calculated by an inbuilt function in the `tinygps++` library and gives result in meter.

7 Experiment

We got experimental results of speed, location, and distance within acceptable accuracy. Since Neo 6m GPS has a horizontal accuracy of 2.5m(As per datasheet), this result can be said to be correct.

Figure 3. Speed value in serial monitor of Arduino, during a ride with our device

Figure 2. Speed and distance data in OLED Screen

8 Conclusions

Our goal to make such a device that can track location and speed limit in the accidental or restricted area is fulfilled. We have measured everything within acceptable accuracy. However, to imply this work practically in large scale, some modifications are needed. After some modifications, we hope that it will be very effective to reduce road accidents especially in accidental zone.

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